

TRANSFORMATION THEORY FOR THE PHYSICAL
AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES

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The prediction of effective mechanical and physical properties of multi-phase solids is one of the major concerns in the theory for composites. At the ICCM-I it was emphasized (Hashin 1975) that the same mathematics is involved in the prediction of a wide range of physical properties including the tensors of dielectric permittivity and magnetic permeability. The problems of determining the effective physical properties of composite materials therefore constitute a class of identical mathematical problems referred to as the "dielectric problem." There are also clear parallels between the dielectric problem and the problem of determining the elastic moduli of composite materials; but the fact that the physical properties are represented by tensors of rank 2 or 3 while the tensor of elastic moduli is of rank 4 appears at first sight to present a difficulty. The paper will show how this difficulty is removed.

A number of approaches are available for calculating this transformation theory to obtain the bulk- and shear moduli of a composite consisting of an elastic matrix with a dilute random dispersion of spherical inclusions. In the dilute case it can be assumed that there is no elastic interaction between the inclusions. Each inclusion makes its contribution to the internal stress independently of its neighbours. This is the basic assumption in Eshelby's calculation which provides first order approximations to the moduli. However, it was recently found (Pedersen and Brown 1977, Pedersen 1977) that inclusion-inclusion interaction can be included via a mean field assumption. Essentially this assumption expresses the lack of detailed information on the structure of the composite, and it is found that the mean field model is equivalent to Hashin and Shtrikman's (1963) variational theory. The mean field model has been worked out for the general case of an anisotropically elastic matrix with aligned anisotropic ellipsoidal inclusions. The ellipsoids represents a wide range of inclusion shapes, including spheres and fibres, so the mean field model refers to both particulate and fibrous composites. The best lower bound for the 6 x 6 matrix of elastic compliances obtained from the mean field model is

$$M^C = M^M + fA^{-1}(L^M - L^I)M^M$$

where A^{-1} is the inverse of the 6 x 6 matrix

$$A = fL^I + (1-f)(L^M - (L^M - L^I)S)$$

where L is the 6×6 matrix of elastic stiffnesses, f is the volume fraction of inclusions, S is a 6×6 matrix version of Eshelby's fourth rank tensor, S_{ijkl} and suffixes C , I and M refer to composite, inclusion and matrix, respectively. The best upper bound is obtained by swapping the roles of matrix and inclusions.

In the paper it will be shown how the elastostatic transformation theory is translated into a magnetostatic theory, and hence a theory appropriate for dealing with the dielectric problem. The M^C expression is translated into an expression for μ_{ij}^C , the second rank tensor for the magnetic permeability. It is demonstrated that μ_{ij}^C for spherical inclusions and magnetically isotropic phases is identical to Hashin and Shtrikman's (1963) expression for a 2-phase solid. Extensions of the present approach are discussed with special consideration of possible applications to the potentially important product properties described by Albers (1975) at the ICCM-I.